

INVARIANCE UNDER CORDIALITY OF PATH UNION OF $C_5 \circ P_k$

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Abstract:

We obtain different structures of $P_m(G)$ for $G = C_5 \circ P_k$. We take $k=2,3,4,5,6$. The different structures are obtained on path union because of we use different vertices on $C_5 \circ P_k$ to construct $P_m(G)$. We show all structures so obtained are cordial. Hence invariance under cordiality.

Keywords: *Invariance; Cordial Labeling; Path Union; Path; Cycle.*

Cite This Article: Mukund V.Bapat. (2018). "INVARIANCE UNDER CORDIALITY OF PATH UNION OF $C_5 \circ P_k$." *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 5(3), 116-122. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1216825.

1. Introduction

The graphs we consider are simple, finite, undirected and connected. For terminology and definitions we depend on Graph Theory by Harary [6], A dynamic survey of graph labeling by J.Gallian [8] and Douglas West. [9]. I.Cahit introduced the concept of cordial labeling [5]. $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a function. From this label of any edge (uv) is given by $|f(u) - f(v)|$. Further number of vertices labeled with 0 i.e. $v_f(0)$ and the number of vertices labeled with 1 i.e. $v_f(1)$ differ at most by one. Similarly number of edges labeled with 0 i.e. $e_f(0)$ and number of edges labeled with 1 i.e. $e_f(1)$ differ at most by one. Then the function f is called as cordial labeling. I.Cahit has shown that: every tree is cordial; K_n is cordial if and only if $n \leq 3$; $K_{m,n}$ is cordial for all m and n ; the friendship graph $C_3^{(t)}$ (i.e., the one-point union of t copies of C_3) is cordial if and only if t is not congruent to 2 (mod 4); all fans are cordial; the wheel W_n is cordial if and only if n is not congruent to 3 (mod 4). A lot of work has been done in this type of labeling. One may refer dynamic survey by J. Gallian [8].

Our focus of attention is on path unions on different graphs. For a given graph there are different path unions (up to isomorphism) structures possible. It depends on which point on G is used to fuse with vertex of P_m to obtain path-union. We have shown that for $G = \text{bull on } C_3, \text{ bull on } C_4, C_3^+, C_4^+ - e$ then different path union $P_m(G)$ are cordial [4]. It is called as invariance under cordial labeling. We use the convention that $v_f(0,1) = (a,b)$ to indicate the number of vertices labeled with 0 are a in number and that number of vertices labeled with 1 are b in number. Further $e_f(0,1) = (x,y)$ we mean the number of edges labeled with 0 are x and number of edges labeled with 1 are y in number. The graph whose cordial labeling is known is cordial graph.

2. Preliminaries

Fusion of vertex Let G be a (p,q) graph. Let $u \neq v$ be two vertices of G . We replace them with single vertex w and all edges incident with u and that with v are made incident with w . If a loop is formed is deleted. The new graph has $p-1$ vertices and at least $q-1$ edges. [9]. **Path union of G** , i.e. $P_m(G)$ is obtained by taking a path p_m and take m copies of graph G . Then fuse a copy each of G at every vertex of path at given fixed point on G . It has mp vertices and $mq + m-1$ edges. Where G is a (p,q) graph.

3. Theorems Proved

3.1. Theorem: All structures of $P_m(G)$ are cordial for $G = C_5 \Theta P_2$

Proof: Define $f: V(P_m(G)) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows. f gives two labeled copies of $C_5 \Theta P_2$ Type A and Type B. These are shown in fig 5.1 and fig 5.2 below.

Fig 5.1 $v_f(0,1)=(5,5)$, $e_f(0,1) =$

Fig 5.2 $v_f(0,1)=(5,5)$, $e_f(0,1) = (5,5)$

There are two structures possible on $P_m(G)$. In **structure1** we choose vertex 'a' from type A and 'b' from Type B to fuse on vertex of path $P_m = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m)$. In **structure2** we choose vertex 'c' from type A and vertex 'd' from Type B to fuse on vertex of path P_m . Note that any of the 5 pendent vertices each from Type A and that from Type B will be vertex 'a' or vertex 'b' respectively. And any of the 5 degree three vertices from each type A and Type B will be vertex 'c' and 'd' respectively.

Fig 5.3 Labeled copy of $P_4(C_5 \Theta P_2)$: $v_f(0,1)=(20,20)$, $e_f(0,1) = (22,21)$; structure1

Structure 1: We start with a unlabeled path P_m and at vertex v_i on it fuse vertex 'a' from type A if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex 'b' from type b if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. The label of edge (aa) = label of edge (bb) = 0 and label of edge (ab) = 1. The label numbers in this case are $v_f(0,1)=(5m,5m)$ for all m

and for edges when $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ we have $e_f(0,1) = (5m+x, 5m+x-1)$ and when m is of type $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2 \dots$ we have $e_f(0,1) = (5m+x, 5m+x)$.

For **structure 2** we repeat the same procedure as above. We start with a unlabeled path P_m and at vertex v_i on it fuse vertex 'c' from type A if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex 'd' from type b if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. The label of edge (cc) = label of edge (dd) = 0 and label of edge (cd) = 1. The label numbers in this case are $v_f(0,1) = (5m, 5m)$ for all m and for edges when $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ we have $e_f(0,1) = (5m+x, 5m+x-1)$ and when m is of type $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2 \dots$ we have $e_f(0,1) = (5m+x, 5m+x)$.
The graph is cordial. #.

3.2. Theorem: All structures of $P_m(G)$ are cordial for $G = C_5 \circ P_3$.

Proof: Define $f: V(P_m(G)) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows. f gives two labeled copies of $C_5 \circ P_2$ Type A and Type B. These are shown in fig 5.3 and fig 5.4 below.

Fig 5.4 $v_f(0,1) = (8,7), e_f(0,1) = (8,7)$

Fig 5.5 $v_f(0,1) = (7,8), e_f(0,1) = (8,7)$

Different structures on path union are due to we use different vertices on G namely 'a', 'b' and 'c' to fuse with vertex of $P_m = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m)$

In **structure 1** we fuse vertex 'a' from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex 'd' from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge (ad) = 1 and label (da) = 1. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (8+15x, 7+15x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1) = (15x, 15x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (8m, 8m-1)$.

In **structure 2** we fuse vertex 'b' from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex 'e' from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge (be) = 1 and label (eb) = 1. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (8+15x, 7+15x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1) = (15x, 15x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (8m, 8m-1)$.

In **structure 3** we fuse vertex 'c' from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex 'f' from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge (cf) = 1 and label (fc) = 1. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (8+15x, 7+15x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1) = (15x, 15x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (8m, 8m-1)$. Thus the graph is cordial on all of its structures.

3.3. Theorem: All structures of $P_m(G)$ are cordial for $G = C_5 \odot P_4$

Proof: Define $f: V(P_m(G)) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows. f gives two labeled copies of $C_5 \odot P_4$ Type A and Type B. These are shown in fig 5.6 and fig 5.7 below. They have equal label numbers but different distribution.

In **structure 1** we fuse vertex ‘a’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex ‘x’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. On P_m the label of edge $(ax) = 1$ and $label(xa) = 1, label$ of edge $(xx) = 0$ and $label(aa) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1)=(10m,10m)$ for all m and when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x= 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1)=(10m+x,10m+x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x= 1, 2, \dots$ for all m $e_f(0,1) = (10m, 10m-1)$.

In **structure 2** we fuse vertex ‘b’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex ‘y’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. On P_m the label of edge $(by) = 1$ and $label(yb) = 1, label$ of edge $(yy) = 0$ and $label(bb) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1)=(10m,10m)$ for all m and when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x= 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1)=(10m+x,10m+x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x= 1, 2, \dots$ for all m $e_f(0,1) = (10m, 10m-1)$.

In **structure 3** we fuse vertex ‘c’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex ‘z’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. On P_m the label of edge $(cz) = 1$ and $label(xc) = 1, label$ of edge $(zz) = 0$ and $label(cc) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1)=(10m,10m)$ for all m and when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x= 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1)=(10m+x,10m+x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x= 1, 2, \dots$ for all m $e_f(0,1) = (10m, 10m-1)$.

In **structure 4** we fuse vertex ‘q’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and vertex ‘d’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m if $i \equiv 2, 3 \pmod{4}$. On P_m the label of edge $(qd) = 1$ and $label(dq) = 1, label$ of edge $(qq) = 0$ and $label(dd) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1)=(10m,10m)$ for all m and when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x= 0, 1, 2, \dots$. And $v_f(0,1)=(10m+x,10m+x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x= 1, 2, \dots$ for all m , $e_f(0,1) = (10m, 10m-1)$. The resultant graph structures of $P_m(G)$ are cordial.

3.4. Theorem: All Structures of $P_m(G)$ Are Cordial for $G = C_5 \odot P_5$.

Proof: Define $f: V(P_m(G)) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows. f gives two labeled copies of $C_5 \odot P_2$ Type A and Type B. These are shown in fig 5.8 and fig 5.9 below.

Fig 5.8 $v_f(0,1)=(13,12)$, $e_f(0,1) = (13,12)$

Fig 5.9 $v_f(0,1)=(12,13)$, $e_f(0,1) = (13,12)$

Different structures on path union are due to we use different vertices on G namely ‘e’, ‘a’, ‘b’, ‘c’, ‘d’ to fuse with vertex of $P_m = (v_1, v_2, .. v_m)$.

In **structure 1** we fuse vertex ‘e’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex ‘x’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge $(ex) = 1$ and $label(xe) = 1$, label of edge $(ee) = 0$ and $label(xx) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (13+25x, 12+25x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, ..$, And $v_f(0,1) = (25x, 25x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, ..$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (13m, 13m-1)$.

In **structure 2** we fuse vertex ‘a’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex ‘y’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge $(ay) = 1$ and $label(ya) = 1$, label of edge $(aa) = 0$ and $label(yy) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (13+25x, 12+25x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, ..$, And $v_f(0,1) = (25x, 25x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, ..$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (13m, 13m-1)$.

In **structure 3** we fuse vertex ‘b’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex ‘z’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge $(bz) = 1$ and $label(zb) = 1$, label of edge $(zz) = 0$ and $label(bb) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (13+25x, 12+25x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, ..$, And $v_f(0,1) = (25x, 25x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, ..$. For all m , $e_f(0,1) = (13m, 13m-1)$.

In **structure 4** we fuse vertex ‘c’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex ‘u’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge $(cu) = 1$ and $label(uc) = 1$, label of edge $(uu) = 0$ and $label(cc) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (13+25x, 12+25x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, ..$, And $v_f(0,1) = (25x, 25x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, ..$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (13m, 13m-1)$.

In **structure 5** we fuse vertex ‘d’ from Type A with vertex v_i of P_m and vertex ‘v’ from Type B with vertex v_i of P_m alternately starting with type A. On P_m the label of edge $(dv) = 1$ and $label(vd) = 1$, label of edge $(dd) = 0$ and $label(vv) = 0$. The label number distribution on resultant graph are $v_f(0,1) = (13+25x, 12+25x)$ when m is odd number given by $2x+1, x = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, And $v_f(0,1) = (25x, 25x)$ when m is even number given by $2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$. For all m $e_f(0,1) = (13m, 13m-1)$.

3.5. Theorem: All structures of $P_m(G)$ are cordial for $G = C_5 \square P_6$.

Proof: Define $f: V(P_m(G)) \rightarrow \{0,1\}$ as follows. f gives a labeled copy of $C_5 \square P_2$ namely Type A as shown below. We use it repeatedly in a specific way as shown below to obtain labeled copy of G .

Fig 5.8 $v_f(0,1) = (15,15), e_f(0,1) = (15,15)$

We get 6 different structures on path union depending on the point on $C_5 \square P_6$ fused with vertex of path P_m to obtain $P_m(G)$. We start with a unlabeled copy of P_m .

Structure1: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point ‘a’ on it for $i \equiv 1,2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex ‘x’ if $i \equiv 0,3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$ for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1, x = 0, 1, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$.

Structure2: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point ‘b’ on it for $i \equiv 1,2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex ‘y’ if $i \equiv 0,3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$ for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1, x = 0, 1, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$.

Structure3: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point ‘c’ on it for $i \equiv 1,2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex ‘z’ if $i \equiv 0,3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$ for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1, x = 0, 1, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$.

Structure4: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point ‘d’ on it for $i \equiv 1,2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex ‘u’ if $i \equiv 0,3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$ for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1, x = 0, 1, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x, x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$.

Structure5: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point ‘e’ on it for $i \equiv 1,2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex ‘v’ if $i \equiv 0,3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$

for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1$, $x = 0, 1, \dots$. $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x$, $x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$.

Structure6: At vertex v_i of P_m fuse a labeled copy as above (type A) at point 'f' on it for $i \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{4}$ and at vertex 'w' if $i \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}$. The label number distribution is $v_f(0,1) = (15m, 15m)$ for all m , and on edges when $m = 2x+1$, $x = 0, 1, \dots$. $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x)$ and if $m = 2x$, $x = 1, 2, \dots$ $e_f(0,1) = (15+x, 15+x-1)$. Thus the graph is cordial for all non-isomorphic structures on path union.

4. Conclusions

To obtain a path union we generally fuse a copy of G at a fixed point on G with every vertex of P_m . We have considered every vertex of $C_5 \circ P_k$ that will produce non-isomorphic structure on path union. We take $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$ and 6 . We take all path unions and show that all are cordial. This is also called as invariance under cordiality of path union.

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